

THE PROBLEMS OF SPEECH COMPRESSION IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATIONS

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Introduction: *Simultaneous translation has always aroused an increased interest of foreign and domestic linguists, psycholinguists and psychologists who have studied simultaneous translation proper, or who have used it in as a basis for research in other areas.*

Key words: *oral, written, individual, cultural competency, interpreter, concept, languages, cultures, customs, civilizations, globalization, civilisation, communication effectiveness, translation process.*

In particular, A. A. Leontiev studied the internal program of speech utterance [Leontiev 1969], S. B. Benediktov, D. I. Ermolovich, and a number of other researchers also put forward hypotheses regarding the implementation of the simultaneity of the processes of listening and speaking on the basis of the level distribution of attention, Claude Shannon developed the theory of redundancy of language and speech, V. A. Artemov in his research paid attention to the mechanism for implementing speech compression. The attention of psychologists to simultaneous translation has led to the fact that research in this fields have become, in fact, interdisciplinary. Psycholinguistics has become the basis for studying both simultaneous translation in general and the psychological mechanisms involved in this type of activity (mechanisms of attention, memory, thinking, sensory-perceptual mechanisms, recoding, compression, decompression, switching, level attention mechanism, mechanism of probabilistic forecasting and etc.). This served to develop the theory of translation as a scientific discipline and to understand a number of processes accompanying translation activities,

not amenable to study by means of linguistics alone. The linguistic theory of translation primarily considers the relationship between the translation and the original, and as well as ways to achieve their most complete compliance. Linguists deal with the problem of equivalence, consider various ways of describing the content of a text, means of expressing one and the same content in the texts of the original and translation, the degree of semantic closeness or similarity of the pragmatic impact of these texts. Attempts are also made to identify certain general patterns of the translation process that are present in a large volume of translations and, according to Komissarov V.N., "do not depend on the knowledge, tastes and working conditions of translators" [Komissarov 1997]. Thus, in fact the "human factor" - the personality of the translator - is completely excluded. Considering simultaneous translation from the point of view of psychology, researchers proceed from the understanding of translation activity as a system within which the psyche functions. In the analysis of translation activity, all mental phenomena are considered as peculiar mechanisms. The psychology of translation is based on three interconnected principles - activity, personal and communicative, and also studies a number of other aspects, in particular, the psychology of a translator. In this aspect, individual typological features of the personality are considered (balance, imbalance, excitability-inertia, etc.), and individual psychological characteristics (emotionality, level of intelligence development, character traits, etc.) are also studied. Other areas of research within the psychology of translation include communicative translation activities as such, in particular, the nature and subject of the communicative situation, and also the speech activity of listening and speaking, carried out by the translator in the process of activity, including the content, structural organization and psycholinguistic mechanisms of implementation this activity. In addition to general psychological and specific activity mechanisms (mechanisms of thinking, memory, attention, etc.), mechanisms specific to translation activity, such as switching, recoding, and others, are especially considered.

So, simultaneous translation is defined by various authors as “a combination of continuous perception a translator of speech in one language with the reproduction of its meaning in another” [Benediktov 1968]; like "kind of the activity of an interpreter, characterized by the pronunciation of the text of the translation in parallel with the sound of the original text” [Shiryaev 1979]; as "a form of a complex process of processing information by a person, including the perception, accumulation, search, transformation and transmission of verbal information" [Gerver 1975]; as "such a professional type of interpretation of conferences, which is carried out simultaneously with the perception of the message in the original language with the help of technical means in a specially equipped booth, and in the process of which - in conditions of time pressure - information of a limited volume is processed per unit of text" [Chernov 1969]; as "a type of monologue speech, where the program given from outside” [Leontiev 1969]. In other words, the program of translation activity is determined by the situation specific communicative act and the original text.

Professional simultaneous interpreting is an interpreting carried out under special conditions. For him characterized by unequal conditions for generating speech in the original language and in the target language, lack of time, as well as increased mental tension, the cause of which is the awareness of the synchronism of two activities that take place in the conditions of the loss of the usual forms of control over the speech process, which leads to a feeling of uncertainty about the correctness of actions. The simultaneous translation session lasts for on average within 20-30 minutes. After this, there is a decrease in cognitive activity, a strong fatigue due to intensive involvement in the activity of all mental and nervous processes.

However, simultaneous translation is not only the application of speaking skills in the process of listening. In the basis of the activity of a simultaneous interpreter is not only the spontaneity of speech reproduction, based on sufficient linguistic competence of the interpreter in the source and interpreting languages, but as well as a specific plan of activity that the simultaneous interpreter uses when interpreting.

A communication activity plan is a set of specific strategies used simultaneous interpreter in specific interpreting situations. Among the strategies used in simultaneous interpreting, one can single out, for example, the trial and error strategy, the waiting strategy, the strategy linearity, compression strategy, decompression strategy and others.

Simultaneous translation research has been rather isolated from other research in applied linguistics. The reason for this was the methodological problems caused by the presence of many language pairs, as well as the possibility of practical application of research results in only a relatively narrow area. The first most detailed studies on simultaneous translation were carried out by professional translators who tried to create a theoretical basis for the training of specialists in this field. Subsequent research was a reflection of the main provisions of the cognitive theories. However, despite the fact that after the first attempts to analyze simultaneous translation about half a century has passed, the scientific community has not yet developed a unified position on the issue of research problems of simultaneous translation.

Experimental work in the field of simultaneous translation began to appear in the mid-1960s. century. Issues of interest to researchers included:

- the issue of phase shift and the unit of simultaneous translation;
- general functional mechanisms of speech activity in the process of simultaneous translation;
- the mechanism of level awareness and control over the performance of individual actions and the correctness of the statement;
- the role of pause in simultaneous translation;
- the role of memory in the translation process;
- mechanism of distribution of attention;
- mechanism of probabilistic forecasting and proactive synthesis in the process of perception and generation of speech in simultaneous translation, and others.

These problems were raised and considered in order to prove or disprove the simultaneity of the processes of listening and speaking in the conditions of

simultaneous translation. The simultaneity of these processes was experimentally confirmed in the late 1970s.

In order to test the hypothesis about the synchronism of the processes of listening and speaking, G. V. Chernov and I. A. Zimnyaya conducted research with simultaneous recording of the original and translation into audio equipment. As a result of the experiment, it was found that the translator conveys the meaning of the speaker's statement, which in most cases coincides with the sound of the translator himself with more or less time lag. In this case, if the meaning of the speaker's statement was understood by the interpreter during time of his own speaking, then the processes of perception and speaking can proceed simultaneously in conditions of simultaneous translation [Chernov 1980]. Thus, the simultaneous interpreter simultaneously perceives the speaker's speech program and recodes it into the target language. Complexity simultaneous translation consists in the fact that the translator is forced to build his own program of speech utterance in parallel with the speech program of the speaker, correlating with the semantic reference points in his speech. In accordance with the strategy of probabilistic forecasting, the translator puts forward a hypothetical program for the development of the speaker's speech statement from the very beginning of its sound, and then confirms or refutes his forecast by analyzing the incoming semantic reference points of the speech statement in the source language.

One of the most important issues considered by the theory of simultaneous translation is the nature of the probabilistic forecasting mechanism, which is considered fundamental in the implementation of simultaneous translation. Among the variety of mechanisms involved in the process of simultaneous translation(mechanisms of memory, the mechanism of level distribution of attention, the mechanism of pause and others), the leading G. V. Chernov considers the psycholinguistic mechanism of probabilistic forecasting. When generating speech, the main role is given to the mechanism of preemptive synthesis. The researcher bases his position on the position of the psychology of activity on the counter activity of the brain when perceiving information.

It should be noted that probabilistic forecasting is based on the redundancy of language and speech [Chernov1980]. At the same time, redundancy is understood not as the redundancy of the language in general, but the redundancy of speech in this language. The higher the message redundancy, the higher the probability of a correct prediction. It is known that the redundancy of a developed language is approximately 70-85%. Simultaneous interpreter for practice deals with the redundancy of a coherent message. At the same time, connectivity is based on the unity of the topic. and communicative intention of the speaker [Chernov 1980].

The higher the message redundancy, the more the connection between the communicative intention of the speaker and the unity of the topic, and consequently, the greater the likelihood of using lexical units that can be predetermined by the meaning of the speech.

It should be noted that the level of redundancy of functional styles is quite high (about 96%), so how each functional style is characterized by a certain set of lexical units. Consequently, it is much easier for a simultaneous interpreter to put forward hypotheses, provided that the interpreter knows the vocabulary of this functional style. Obviously, the mechanism of probabilistic forecasting and the concept of language redundancy are closely related to the concept of speech compression, which is based on the psychological and linguistic patterns of speech activity. Information redundancy of speech, in turn, makes it possible to implement a compression strategy in simultaneous translation. Studies have shown that with carefully crafted written translation from English into the Russian syllabic value of the text increases one and a half times, and during oral translation, where there is no possibility to carefully work out the wording, the text can be more than two times larger [Chernov 1969]. At provided that the speaker delivers a speech at an average or fast pace, then it is difficult, and sometimes even impossible, for the interpreter to have time to pronounce the full text of the translation during the time the speaker delivers the speech. Thus, there is a need to deliberately reduce the amount of text in the target language. Among other things, you cannot forget that the speed of speech-thinking operations is finite and is determined by the natural capabilities and abilities of each particular translator. Therefore, an increase in the rate of speech in the source language leads to an increase in the number of translation errors. Finally, in the translator's speech there must be pauses in order for him to be able to hear fragments of the speaker's speech without simultaneously pronouncing the text of the translation (this, in particular, is due to the

fact that the process of speaking the speaker and the process of the interpreter's speaking rarely coincides in time by more than 70%).

Speech compression is "... such a compression of it, determined by the specific conditions of communication, in which only what is necessary for a given task of communication is preserved in it, and everything else is swept aside"[Artemov 1966].

In fact, speech compression is generated by the specific conditions of the simultaneous interpreter's activity (time restrictions and the simultaneity of the processes of listening to the speaker's speech and generating speech in the target language), and its size is determined by the need to maintain an even pace of the translator's speech in the target language. Speech compression, therefore, is a form of adaptation of translation actions to the conditions of activity.

In particular, G. V. Chernov identified the size of compression by comparing compressed texts obtained as a result of simultaneous translation with uncompressed texts performed by in writing. As a result, it turned out that the compression during translation can reach 30-37%. The main factor affecting the size of the compression of the original message is the speed of the speaker's speech.

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